
HOUSEHOLDS' CONSUMPTION PATTERNS OF GRASSCUTTER (*Thryonomys swinderianus*) MEAT WITHIN IBADAN METROPOLIS, OYO STATE, NIGERIA.

Odebode, A.V.; Awe, F.; Famuyide, O.O.; Adebayo, O.; Ojo, O.B. and Daniel, G.

Department of Forest Economics and Extension, Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, P.M.B.5054, Jericho Hills, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The study was aimed at determining household consumption patterns of grasscutter meat within Ibadan Metropolis. Primary data were sourced by the use of 120 copies of structured questionnaire out of which 115 copies were analyzed. A multistage random sampling procedure was applied in administering the questionnaires. Descriptive statistics as well as Chi-square were used to analyze the data. The findings showed that 59% of the respondents were male while 48% were female. Ninety eight percent (98%) also attested that consumption of grasscutter meat has no contradiction on their culture. About 54% of the respondents were married, 24% were single and about 22% were both divorced, widow and widower. It was discovered that 71% had formal education and 28.7% had either informal or no education. From the findings, 68% of the consumers ate grasscutter meat because of its taste while 19.1% ate it because of its nutritional value. Chi-square analysis showed that age, marital status, educational level, income and occupation were statistically significant to households' consumption pattern at 5% level of significance, while religion was not significant. This implies that age, marital status, educational level and occupation have influence on the grasscutter consumption patterns of the consumers. Based on the findings from the study, it was therefore recommended that more training on the domestication of grasscutter should be made available to consumers in order to reduce scarcity of the meat due to seasonality. This will also reduce the price of grasscutter meat, especially during the raining season.

KEYWORDS: Grasscutter, perception, households, Ibadan, bushmeat, Chi-square

INTRODUCTION

Wild animals often known as bushmeat throughout West African region are highly valued forest products. A significant proportion of the population living in rural areas depends so much on these forest resources for their sustenance (FOS, 1999). They provide an important source of meat in both rural and urban household diets. Forests and fallow fields provide the habitat for many commonly consumed wildlife species. Wildlife is a potential source of animal protein and income for rural households. The most commonly hunted species are bats, squirrels, grasscutter, giant rats, guinea fowl and snakes (Adeola and Decker, 1987), while many households already have a few domestic animals such as chickens, sheep or goats. These animals are regularly consumed only on ceremonial and festival occasions and do not supply a regular source of food (Ajayi, 1979 and Asibey, 1974).

There has been a growing body of literature on the importance of bushmeat in the West African forest sub-region. Information on consumption is often based upon an estimate of the number of people who consume bushmeat (e.g. 72% of southern Nigerians consume giant rat (Ajayi and Olawoye, 1974) or the percentage contribution of bushmeat to the diet (e.g in Cameroonian forest zone, bushmeat supplies 70-89% of animal protein (Prescott-Allen et al, 1982). Bushmeat has an important nutritional role in the diet. It adds flavor and diversity and encourages people to consume greater quantities of staple foods while providing them with vitamins and minerals (Annegers, 1973).

According to FAO (2003), bushmeat consumption is a common occurrence in various areas in Africa where wild animals are hunted for the consumer market by professional hunters and agriculturists. Bushmeat plays a very significant role in the maintenance of communities' livelihoods, food security and nutritional status through subsistence consumption. Traffic(2000) opined that the decrease in standard of living and increase in human populations have resulted in an increased demand for bushmeat , with the resultant decline in availability in most parts of the West African region (FDF, Nigeria, 1987). This may not be unconnected with the increasing

demand for bushmeat by the urban dwellers (Awe *et al*, 2009a, Ntiamo-Baidu, 1987). Bushmeat is valued throughout the West African region as a source of income and food (Martin, 1983). Ayodele (1992) revealed that 15% of the animal protein consumed by rural inhabitants of southern Nigeria is obtained from bushmeat and this was valued at over nine million naira (N9, 000,000).

Prominent among the consumed bushmeat is grasscutter, also known as cane rat, has the scientific name of *Thryonomys swinderianus*. Grasscutter is a robust animal with short tails, small ears and stocky body. There are two common species- the large species (*Thryonomys swinderianus*) which is the focus of this study and it weighs up to 9kg or more with body length of up to 60cm. The smaller species (*Thryonomys gregorianus*) may occasionally reach 8kg and a body length of up to 50cm. They both have yellowish-brown bodies with whitish bellies. The fur is coarse and firm. The grasscutter is a wild hystricomorphic rodent hunted particularly in Africa for its meat (Adoun, 1993; Ntiamo-Baidu, 1998). It is the biggest rodent after the crested porcupine (*hystrix cristata*) weighing averagely 13kg in Africa. Grasscutter according to Adoun(1992b) is found only in Africa in grasslands and wooded savannahs throughout the humid and sub-humid areas south of Sahara(NRC, 1991). It is very desirable for domestication because of its excellent taste and comparatively higher nutritional value (Asibey and Eyeson, 1973) and meat yield(Clottey, 1981) than most small livestock species.

Mensah(2005) observed that about 40,000 tonnes of grasscutter meat was consumed in West Africa annually, of which only a small proportion was provided by domestication. Grasscutter meat is a good alternative for regular sources of protein which have become quite scarce in Nigeria (Adesope, 1996). This is because the live animals stay in the wild and getting them easily and readily remains a challenge (Edna *et al.*, 2008). Great quantities of the meat, according to Hladik *et al.* (1987) are generally consumed throughout the West African sub- region. This may be due to the fact that they are more available during the raining season because of the heavy presence of reeds and herbaceous vegetation that can provide them with good cover (Awe *et al*, 2009a). Ogebe *et al.* (1996) had shown that in Benue State grasscutter meat is known by the people and available for sale in their locality regularly throughout the wet season from hunting activities. It was reported that grasscutter exists in a high social hierarchy and seldom migrates. Eniang *et al* (1996) were of the view that city dwellers cherish grasscutter as it is popularly called. They further explained that one of the prominent wildlife that people have taste for and features relatively regularly in their meals is grasscutter. However, the extent to which people purchase and consume grasscutter meat often varies considerably with household and community (Dietwort, 1987).

Grasscutter meat is cholesterol-free; having higher dressing percentage of about 65% excluding the head and it is socially and culturally very acceptable with no religious taboos against its meat consumption and it is an animal in great demand. According to Edna *et al.* (2008), grasscutter meat is relatively more expensive than other meat types, yet it is highly demanded and consumed by individuals both in homes and restaurants in Nigeria. This study, therefore, was set out to assess the consumption of grasscutter meat within Ibadan

Metropolis with the following specific objectives:

- ❖ To determine the availability of grasscutter meat in the study area
- ❖ To identify why and who consume grasscutter meat.
- ❖ To determine the relationship between households' socioeconomic characteristics and their consumption pattern of grasscutter meat.
- ❖ To identify problems and difficulties confronting households in getting grasscutter meat

METHODOLOGY

Study Area: The study was carried out in Ibadan Metropolis, the capital city of Oyo State, Nigeria. Ibadan is located approximately on Longitude 3°5' East of the Greenwich Meridian and Latitude 7°23' North of the Equator. There are eleven Local Government Areas (LGAs) within Ibadan out of which five are urban while the remaining six are semi-urban LGAs (NPC, 2006). The urban are Ibadan North, Ibadan North East, Ibadan North West, Ibadan South East and Ibadan Southwest while the semi-urban are Akinyele, Egbeda, Iddo, Lagelu, Ona-Ara and Oluyole LGAs.

Data Collection: One hundred and twenty (120) copies of structured questionnaire and oral interview were used to elicit information for both pre-survey test and final information. But only one hundred and fifteen were found analyzable. At least twenty households per Local Government Area (LGA) were randomly selected from five (5) of the eleven (11) LGAs that make up the Metropolis. One consumer per household was randomly selected.

The five selected LGAs were Akinyele, Ibadan Northwest, Ibadan Southwest, Ibadan North and Iddo Local Government Areas.

Method Data Analysis: Descriptive statistics such as percentages and frequencies as well as inferential statistics such as Chi square were used in analyzing the data.

$$\text{Chi Square}(X^2) = \sum (O-E/E)^2$$

Where O = Observed frequency

E = Expected frequency

\sum = Summation sign

Hypothesis: The null hypothesis (H_0) says there is no significant relationship between the socioeconomic characteristics (age, income, religion, marital status, educational level, occupation) of consumers and their grasscutter consumption pattern

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the socioeconomic characteristics of consumers. The results showed that about 17% of the consumers were less than 30 years while about 43% were between 30 and 50 years of age and those that were 51 years and above accounted for about 41%. This is an indication that the consumption of grasscutter meat cuts across different age groups and most of the consumers were still within the working age group and can easily move around to source for the meat. On gender distribution, 59% of the respondents were male while female accounted for 41%. This implies that both male and female consume grasscutter and its consumption has no gender barrier. From the results, it was also evident that grasscutter meat has no social or cultural barrier as 98% of the consumers opined the consumption of grasscutter has no effect on their culture. In addition, 34.8% of the consumers were Christians while 39.1% practice Islamic religion and 26.1% of them said they practice traditional religion. This implies that the consumption of grasscutter meat is acceptable to all religions as it was evident in the observations of the consumers where 96% of them said the consumption has no effect on their religion.

It could also be observed from Table 1 that about 54% of the consumers were married while about 24% of them were single and close to 22% of the consumers were either divorced, widows or widowers. From the educational distribution in Table 1, about 71% of the consumers had formal education and at least primary education while 18.3% had no formal education and 10.4% had other forms of education like Arabic education. It was also discovered from the study that the tribe of the consumers does not affect the consumption of the meat as Yoruba, Igbo and Hausa do eat grasscutter. Majority, 37.4%, of the consumers earned above N 30,000 monthly and only about 16% had their monthly income less than N10, 000, as shown in Table1. This implies that most of the consumers were within the high income group.

Findings from the study also revealed that people liked and ate grasscutter meat, while about 68% of the consumers ate the meat because of its taste, 19.1% of them ate it because of its nutritional value, as seen in Figure1. These observations agree with Awe *et al* (2009a) which reported that majority, 76%, of the people eat grasscutter meat because of its taste. Nearly 49% of the consumers described the taste as moderate. It was also observed that 13% of them were undecided about the taste. Owing to the taste and quality of the meat, 96% of the consumers said they would prefer grasscutter meat to other meat types, as shown in Table3. From Table4, majority of the consumers, 45.2%, got their meat from hunters while close to 23%, each got theirs from the market or other sources such as restaurants. None of the consumers got their meat from either research institutes or through domestication. This may not be unconnected with non availability of grasscutter in research institutes in commercial quantities and other allied organizations as well as lack or inadequate awareness of the people on the domestication of grasscutter.

Table1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of Consumers

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
<u>Age</u>		
<30	19	16.5
30-50	49	42.6
51-70	29	25.2
Above 70	18	15.7
Total	115	100
<u>Gender</u>		
Male	68	59
Female	47	41
Total	115	100
<u>Religion</u>		
Christianity	40	34.8
Islam	45	39.1
Traditional	30	26.1
Total	115	100
<u>Marital status</u>		
Single	28	24.3
Married	62	53.9
Divorced	7	6.1
Widow(er)	18	15.7
Total	115	100
<u>Educational level</u>		
No formal	21	18.3
Primary	27	23.5
Secondary	20	17.4
Post secondary	35	30.4
Others	12	10.4
Total	115	100
<u>Tribe</u>		
Yoruba	61	53
Hausa	18	15.7
Igbo	20	17.4
Others	16	13.9
Total	115	100
<u>Occupation</u>		
Artisan	23	20
Civil servant	29	25.2
Farmer	11	9.6
Trader	36	31.3
Others	16	13.9
Total	115	100
<u>Income (N)</u>		
<10,000	18	15.6
10,000-20,000	20	17.4
21,000-30,000	34	29.6
>30,000	43	37.4
Total	115	100

Source: Field survey, 2011

Table2: Description of Taste/Quality

Taste	Frequency	Percentage
High	56	48.7
Moderate	37	32.2
Low	7	6.1
Undecided	15	13.0
Total	115	100

Source: Field survey, 2011

Table3: Preference for Grasscutter meat

Prefer	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	110	96
No	5	4
Total	115	100

Source: Field survey, 2011

Table4: Source of Grasscutter meat and Consumption Pattern

Source	Frequency	Percentage
Market	26	22.6
Bush	11	9.6
Research Institute	–	–
Domestication	–	–
Hunters	52	45.2
Others	26	22.6
Total	115	100
Consumption Pattern		
Everyday	9	7.8
Once a week	23	20
Once a month	35	30.4
Irregularly	48	41.7
Total	115	100

Source: Field survey, 2011

Table5: Availability of Grasscutter

Availability	Frequency	Percentage
Readily available	9	7.8
Available	37	32.2
Not Available	46	40
No comment	23	20
Total	115	100

Source: Field survey, 2011

Table6: Effect of Price Increase on Consumption

Effect	Frequency	Percentage
Increase Consumption	9	8
Decrease Consumption	39	34
No effect	67	58
Total	115	100

Source: Field survey, 2011

Figure1: Reason for Consuming Grasscutter

Figure2: Constraints to Availability of Grasscutter Meat

In addition, about 8% of the consumers claimed they consumed grasscutter meat on a daily basis while majority (about 42%) of them said they consumed it on an irregular basis. This may not be unconnected with inadequate availability of the meat as 40% of the consumers said the meat was not available, as shown in Table5. However, 58% of the consumers said any increase in the price of the meat will not affect their consumption level, as can be seen in Table6. This is contrary to what is expected of a Normal Good. However, 34% of them expect that an increase in price will reduce their consumption. This corroborates the law of demand which states that an increase in the price of a commodity will cause a fall in the quantity of that commodity that will be demanded. In addition, 8% of the consumers claimed an increase in the price of the meat will cause a rise in their consumption level. This would be a case of an abnormal demand curve where people may attribute high price to high quality, thereby increasing their purchases of a commodity even with increase in price of the commodity.

Table7 shows Chi-square analysis testing the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics (age, income, religion, marital status, educational level, occupation) of consumers and their consumption pattern of grasscutter. In other words, the test was to find out whether there was any significant relationship between the selected socioeconomic characteristics of the consumers and how often they consume grasscutter meat. It was therefore discovered that age, income, marital status, educational level and occupation were statistically significant while religion was not significant. This implies that religion has nothing to do with the consumption of grasscutter.

Table7: Chi-square Analysis Showing Relationship between Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents and their Consumption Pattern

Variable	X ²	df	P	Decision
Age	21.59	3	<0.05	Significant
Income	12.17	4	<0.05	Significant
Religion	4.19	2	>0.05	Not significant
Marital status	58.94	3	<0.05	Significant
Educational level	12.78	4	<0.05	Significant
Occupation	17.31	4	<0.05	Significant

Source: Chi-square Analysis

Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between socioeconomic characteristics of consumers and the consumption of grasscutter meat holds for religion and is rejected for age, income, marital status, education and occupation of consumers.

Findings from the study revealed that people like and cherish grasscutter meat and would eat it as much as they get it. However, various reasons were given as constraints to regular availability of grasscutter meat. Some of these include seasonality which accounted for 34% of the consumers as well as price, proximity, government policies and many others as shown in Figure 2.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The households' consumption patterns of grasscutter meat has been studied and analyzed. Grasscutter consumption cuts across different age groups and it has no gender, cultural and religious barrier.

Grasscutter is also highly cherished by the populace mainly because of its good taste and it is highly preferred to other meat types. However, its availability is not regular and this affects the people's consumption pattern. This may be due to the fact that grasscutter has not been reared on a large scale as well as lack or inadequate awareness and training of the people on domestication of grasscutter. The Chi-square analysis revealed that age, marital status, educational level, and occupation have significant relationship with the perception of the consumers towards grasscutter meat consumption at 5 percent significant level.

Since the people are ready to consume more of this meat than any other meat, it is therefore recommended that research institute and other related organizations should intensify efforts in training more people on the domestication of grasscutter. This will go a long way in ensuring the regular availability of grasscutter meat and stabilizing the price. It will also serve as a source of employment generation to a great number of the unemployed. Fund should also be made available by government to interested individuals on the domestication of grasscutter in order to establish their own business. Furthermore, research institutes, especially Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), the mass media and other agencies should create more awareness about the domestication of grasscutter.

REFERENCES

- Adeola, M.O. and Decker, E. (1987): Wildlife Utilization in Rural Nigeria. Paper presented at the International Symposium of Wildlife Management in Sub-Saharan Africa, sponsored by FAO and the International Council for Game and Wildlife Conservation, 6th-13th October, Harare, Zimbabwe, pp.512-521.
- Adesope, O.M. (1996): Using Social Action Process to increase Grasscutter Production: Implication for Extension Services. Nigeria Society for Animal Production (NSAP) Conference at the University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- Adoun, C. (1993): Place De L'aulacode (*Thryonomys swinderianus*) Dans Le Regne Animal Et Sa Repatrition Geographique. Pp. 35-40 In "1er Conference Internationale L'auladodiculture: Acquis Et Perspective."
- Ajayi, S.S.(1978). Pattern of bushmeat production, preservation and marketing in West Africa. *Nigerian Journal of Forestry* 8(1): 48-52.
- Ajayi, S.S. and Olawoye, O.O. (1974). Some indications of the social acceptance of the African giant rat (*Crycetomys gambianus*) in southern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Forestry* 4(1): 36-41.

- Annegers, J. F. (1973). Seasonal food shortages in West Africa. *Ecology of Food and Nutrition* 2:251-257.
- Asibey, E.D.A., and K.K. Eyeson, (1973). Additional information on the importance of wild animals as food source in South Africa of the Sahara, Bungo. *J. Ghana Wildlife Soc.*, 1: 13-17.
- Ayodele, I.A. (1992): Snail propagation: a cheap source of lean meat for the household. Proceedings of Training of Trainers (TOT) workshop on small livestock production under the household security and nutrition. UNICEF publication. Pp 10-21.
- Awe F, Idumah F O, Imoagene E and Eniola T S (2009). Socio-economic Characteristics and Rural Households' perception about the consumption of grasscutter (*Thryonomys swinderianus*) meat in selected LGAs of Kogi State. *Journal of Agriculture, Forestry and the Social Sciences*.7 (1):124-233.
- Clotey, A., (1981). Relation of physical body composition to meat yield in the grasscutter (*Thryonomys swinderianus* Teminx). *Ghana J. Sci.*, 21: 1-7.
- Dietwort, D. (1987). Household meat consumption survey in communities in Southern Nigeria. International Livestock Centre for Africa (ILCA), Humid Zone Programme, Ibadan, Nigeria (Unpublished).
- Edna C Matthews-Njoku; O.M. Adesope and M.B. Nodu (2008): Socio-Economic Characteristics Associated with Rural Households perception about Grasscutter Meat cost in the Niger Delta Zone of Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences* 5(4):360-362
- Eniang, E.A. ;O. Olayide and E.S. Udo (1996): Domestication of Grasscutter: A way of complementing meat production in Nigeria. NSAP Conference Book of Abstracts.
- FAO (2003): Forestry Outlook Study for Africa. Regional report-opportunity and Challenges towards 2020.FAO. Forestry Paper 141. African Development Bank, European Commission, Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, Rome, 2003.
- Federal Department of Forestry(1987): Wildlife utilization and Wildlife Values in Nigeria. Paper presented at the International Symposium and Conference; Wildlife Management in Sub-Saharan Africa, Harare, 6th-13th October. Sponsored by FAO and the International Council for Game and Wildlife Conservation.
- Federal Office of Statistics (1999): Poverty Profile for Nigeria: 1980-1996. Federal Office of Statistics, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Hladik, C. et al (1987). Se nourrir en foret equatorial: anthropologie alimentaire Differentielle des populations des regions forestieres humides d'Afrique. Research Team Report 263, Centre Nationale de Recherches Scientifiques, Paris, France.
- Martin, G.H. (1983). Bushmeat in Nigeria as a natural resource with environmental implications. *Environmental Conservation*. 10(2):125-132.
- Mensah, G. A. (1995). Consommation et digestibilité alimentaire chez l'aulacode *Thryonomys swinderianus*. *Tropicultura*, 13 (3):123-124.
- NPC (2006): National Population Commission 2006, Abuja, Nigeria
- National Research Council, USA (1991): Microlivestock, Little Known Small Animals with promising economic future.Xvii. National Academic Press, Washington D.C. Pp.449.
- Ntiamao-baidu, Y. (1998). Wildlife development plan 1998-2003: sustainable use of bush meat. Commissioned by Wildlife Department, Accra. Ministry of lands and forestry.
- Ntiamao-Baidu, Y. (1987): West Africa Wildlife: A resource in jeopardy. *Unasylva* 156,39(2):27-35.

Ogebe, P.O.; S.Z. Waziri and A.A. Ndanusa (1996): Possibility of Farming Grasscutter in Benue State. NSAP Conference, UNIUYO.

Traffic (2000): Food for Thought: the utilization of wild meat in Eastern and Southern Africa. Cambridge, United Kingdom. Traffic International.www.traffic.org/whatsnew

Received for Publication: 23/08/2011

Accepted for Publication: 30/11/2011

Corresponding author

Awe, F.

Department of Forest Economics and Extension, Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, P.M.B.5054, Jericho Hills, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

E-mail: femray4real@yahoo.com